

Formulating Principles for Accelerating Microbiome-Based Biomarkers to Clinical Practice

Biomarkers are “biological molecules found in tissues, blood or other body fluids that can be used to follow body processes and diseases in humans and animals” (European Medicines Agency).

In the field of human microbiomes, hundreds of potential biomarkers are discovered each year, but only a few proceed with qualification or clinical implementation.

The Human Microbiome Action project used a robust Delphi survey asking 93 experts from 21 countries to identify needs and propose actions integrating microbiome features into clinical practice through relevant biomarkers in medical decision-making and patient care.

EXPERT PERSPECTIVES: INSIGHTS FROM 90+ DELPHI SURVEY PARTICIPANTS ON MICROBIOME-BASED BIOMARKERS

Recommendations to overcome challenges

Raise awareness about biomarkers.

Promote awareness and adoption of standards and reference materials.

Foster interdisciplinary dialogue and collaborative projects.

Align R&D with clinical expectations for translation into clinical practice.

CONTACT:

info@humanmicrobiomeaction.eu

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CONCLUSION

The Human Microbiome Action project, guided by insights from a comprehensive Delphi survey, emphasises the importance of a unified approach to overcoming the barriers in microbiome research and advancing the qualification of microbiome-based biomarkers. By fostering collaboration among various stakeholders, the project identifies challenges and provides practical recommendations. The concerted effort of academia, industry, regulatory bodies, and policymakers is vital for translating microbiome research into clinical applications, thereby enhancing health diagnostics and treatments globally.

Ready to initiate discussions and engage in collaborative efforts to support microbiome-based biomarker qualification?

Join our Stakeholder Advisory Board to provide strategic advice from an external point of view or engage with the [European Microbiome Centres Consortium](#) to foster interdisciplinary collaboration.

For further information, please visit our website humanmicrobiomeaction.eu. Follow the @SciFoodHealth [Twitter/X](#) and [LinkedIn](#) accounts or connect through the [Sustainable Food Systems Network Microbiome Subgroup](#).

Visit our zenodo.org community for all published and upcoming scientific publications.

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